

METROGLYPH ANALYSIS IN SESAME (*Sesamum indicum* L.) GERMPLASM

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Abstract

Twenty sesame germplasm lines were evaluated to assess the pattern of morphological variation through metroglyph analysis at experimental farm of Department of Agri. Botany, VNMKV Parbhani during 2022-23. Morphological variation was evaluated for seven seed characters. Data on seed characters viz., area, perimeter, size, diameter, roundness, elongation and roughness collected using Biovis PSM-digital seed analyzer. In metroglyph scatter diagram, germplasm lines categorized in to four groups. Group I consist of maximum number of germplasm lines among all. Germplasm lines of sesame falling in one group are closely related while lines belonging to different groups exhibit wide variability. Therefore, the germplasm lines belongs to group I & V or I & VI and group II & V or II & VI can be used as parents in sesame improvement programme. Depend on index score genotype EC-204830 is of maximum genetic worth followed by IC-305970, IC-383296, IC-510984 and IC-52554 identified as important in sesame breeding programme.

Key words: Metroglyph, rays, variability, sesame.

Introduction:

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is one of the important oilseed crops of India. It is counted as one of the most 3 ancient oilseed crops of India after Groundnut, Rapeseed and Mustard. Sesame is a self-pollinated crop, with a varying degree of cross pollination depends upon the different influencing factors. It is considered as the "Queen of Oilseeds". Sesame seeds contain 40 to 54 per cent oil which is rich in antioxidants and has a significant amount of oleic and linoleic acids (Abate and Mekbib 2015). Sesame is an important annual oilseed crop in the tropics and warm subtropics. In India, total oilseed crops are grown on 28.79 million hectares land along with production of 36.10 million tonnes and a productivity of 1254 kg/ha. In Maharashtra, the productivity of sesame is less as compared to other oilseeds that need be increased for meeting the requirement of the state.

In order to increase the range and profitability of sesame cultivation, it is imperative to take use of the outstanding gene pool. For any crop improvement programme, genetic variability is key component. Genetic variability for agronomic characters is a important component for broadening the gene pool of crops. The knowledge of variation existing in germplasm is an important and essential aspect for initiating any crop breeding programme (Punitha *et al.*, 2010). The distribution of genetic variability in different plant species depends not only on their evolution and breeding systems but also on ecological, geographical and human factors (Ramanatha and Hodgkin, 2002). Morphological traits were the primary parameters to estimate genetic divergence among sesame cultivars. Metroglyph is a semi-graphical approach for deciphering the morphological variations existing among the population. The results of this technique is more reliable as it is based on the first order statistics and the results can be easily interpreted. Metroglyph analysis and index scoring have been used as useful tool, to access genetic variability among population (Singh and Chowdhury, 1974, Venkatrao *et al.* 1973). Thus, the present investigation was conducted to study variations in sesame genotypes.

Materials and method:

The material for present investigation consist of twenty different indigenous and exotic collections. The experiment was conducted using randomized block design with two replications at experimental farm of Department of Agril. Botany, VNMKV Parbhani during 2022-23. Each genotype was assigned to a single row per plot of 4.5 m length in each replication. The row to row and plant to plant distance was kept at 45 and 10 cm, respectively. The data was collected on seven seed characters viz., seed area, perimeter, size, diameter, roundness, elongation and roughness using Biovis PSM-digital seed analyzer.

The mean for each accession was worked out for each character and range was recorded. The mean data was used to construct the

metroglyph analysis as per the model suggested by Anderson (1957). In this, the glyphs were first plotted on the basis of two extremely variable traits namely seed perimeter (X axis) and seed area (Y axis) all the other characters were represented by rays on the glyph (Fig. 1). Each ray represents a particular character obtained by dividing the range of variation into three equal classes giving the grades low, medium and high for each character. The length of ray assigned to the characters depends upon the index scores of accessions for those characters. The glyph positions and rays were used to assess the variability pattern and correlated traits for assessment of their divergent groups. Each germplasm accession has a special number and is represented as a glyph which is the intersection point of mean values of X and Y co-ordinates.

Result and Discussion:

Among the traits studied, maximum variability was observed in seed perimeter followed by seed area, size, diameter, elongation, roundness and roughness. As traits, seed perimeter and seed area exhibit maximum variability. They are used as X and Y axis respectively. Using mean values of these traits, 20 germplasm lines were plotted as glyph in scatter diagram. The scatter diagram divide seed perimeter; low (5.5-6.1mm), medium (6.1-6.7mm) & high (6.7-7.1mm) and seed area; low (2.75-3.35mm²), medium (3.35-3.95 mm²) & high (3.95-4.55 mm²) in to 3 arbitrary groups each, so as to made maximum 9 groups. Variations for other traits viz., size, diameter, elongation, roundness and roughness were represented by variations in length of corresponding rays on all glyphs.

In metroglyph scatter diagram, germplasm lines categorized in to four groups. Sesame genotypes fell in different four groups, presented in Table 2. Group I with minimum area and minimum perimeter had maximum nine genotypes. It includes four indigenous germplasms viz., IC-140282, IC-396432, IC-396430 and IC-418029 while five exotic germplasm like EC-346243, EC-370850, EC-204614, EC-370741 and EC-370741. As these indigenous and exotic collections belong to same group means they are closely related. Germplasm line IC-140282 found with least area and least perimeter. Three clusters of two genotypes each found in this group indicate their close relation. Germplasm line EC-413256 lie on boundary of group I and II and closely related to EC-370741. Group II with minimum area and medium perimeter consist of three genotypes including two indigenous IC-129417, IC-96129 and one exotic EC-204830 line. Group III and IV do not have any Germplasm. Group V with medium area and medium perimeter consist of four genotypes viz., IC-415615, IC-129746, IC-501607 and EC-346300 in which IC-129746 and EC-346300 form a cluster. Group VI with medium area and maximum perimeter consist of four genotypes IC-305970, IC-383296, IC-510984, IC-52554. Germplasm lines belong to group I and V or I and VI posses variability and can be used as parents

in hybridization programme. Similarly germplasm lines from group II and V or II and VI also possess variability and can be used as parents in hybridization programme (Sasipriya et al., 2022).

Index score of genotypes indicate the genetic worth of germplasm line. The range of index score varied from 7-12. Genotypes with high index score have maximum genetic worth. The germplasm line EC-204830 exhibited maximum index score 12 followed by genotypes IC-305970, IC-383296, IC-510984 and IC-52554 with index score 11 while six germplasm lines recorded with minimum index score 7. Dhanraj (1999) in sesame used metroglyph analysis among sesame genotypes to cluster them into eight groups based on morphological diversity. The application of this technique is still valid in many crops like mungbean (Ahmad et al., 2019), okra (Olayiwola et al., 2021), and rice (Soharu et al., 2021) for the preliminary classification.

The study revealed that, germplasm lines of sesame falling in one group are closely related while lines belonging to different groups exhibit wide variability. Therefore, germplasm lines of sesame falling in different groups can be used as parents in sesame breeding programme. Genotype EC-204830 is of maximum genetic worth followed by IC-305970, IC-383296, IC-510984 and IC-52554 identified as important and can be used in sesame improvement programme.

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Table.1 Index score and ray position of different characters.

Sr. No.	Characters	Glyph position	Range	Mean	Index score		
					1(value<)	2(value from-to)	3(value>)
1	Perimeter	X-axis	5.65-7.11	6.28	6.13	6.13-6.62	6.62
2	Area	Y-axis	2.78-3.88	3.28	3.15	3.15-3.51	3.51
3	Size		2.39-1.91	2.12	2.07	2.07-2.23	2.23
4	Diameter(Avg)		2.01-1.65	1.81	1.77	1.77-1.89	1.89
5	Roundness		1.09-0.99	1.05	1.03	1.03-1.06	1.06
6	Elongation		1.27-1.13	1.19	1.17	1.17-1.21	1.21
7	Roughness		1.20-1.02	1.05	1.08	1.08-1.14	1.14

Table.2 Classification of sesame germplasm lines falling in different groups.

Grouping	No. of genotypes	Germplasm
I	9	IC-140282, IC-396432, EC-346243, IC-396430, EC-370850, EC-204614, IC-418029, EC-370741, EC-413256
II	3	IC-129417, IC-96129, EC-204830
V	4	IC-415615, IC-129746, EC-346300, IC-501607
VI	4	IC-305970, IC-383296, IC-510984, IC-52554

Table.3 Mean performance and index scores of sesame germplasm lines

Sr.No	Genotypes	Area (mm ²)	Perimeter (mm)	Size (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Roundness (mm)	Elongation (mm)	Roughness (mm)
1	IC-140282	2.78	5.65	1.91(1)	1.65(1)	1.09(3)	1.17(1)	1.02(1)
2	IC-396432	2.93	5.82	1.98(1)	1.7(1)	1.08(3)	1.17(1)	1.02(1)
3	EC-346243	2.95	5.89	1.99(2)	1.7(1)	1.07(3)	1.19(2)	1.11(2)
4	IC-396430	2.97	5.92	1.97(1)	1.73(1)	1.07(3)	1.15(1)	1.03(1)
5	EC-370850	3.07	5.97	1.99(1)	1.75(1)	1.08(3)	1.13(1)	1.02(1)
6	EC-204614	3.1	5.98	2.02(1)	1.76(1)	1.08(3)	1.15(1)	1.02(1)
7	IC-418029	3.08	6.06	2.03(1)	1.74(1)	1.07(3)	1.15(1)	1.03(1)
8	EC-370741	3.18	6.07	2.04(1)	1.78(2)	1.07(3)	1.14(1)	1.02(1)
9	EC-413256	3.2	6.1	2.05(1)	1.79(2)	1.08(3)	1.14(1)	1.02(1)
10	IC-129417	3.1	6.17	2.05(1)	1.77(1)	1.05(1)	1.1(1)	1.03(1)
11	IC-96129	3.23	6.18	2.1(2)	1.8(2)	1.05(2)	1.23(3)	1.08(1)
12	EC-204830	3.25	6.28	2.13(2)	1.8(2)	1.04(2)	1.24(3)	1.20(3)
13	IC-415615	3.35	6.27	2.13(2)	1.85(2)	1.07(3)	1.17(1)	1.02(1)
14	IC-129746	3.45	6.4	2.2(2)	1.87(2)	1.06(2)	1.19(2)	1.02(1)
15	EC-346300	3.45	6.44	2.18(2)	1.87(2)	1.05(2)	1.2(2)	1.03(1)
16	IC-501607	3.44	6.55	2.22(2)	1.82(2)	1.02(1)	1.27(3)	1.13(2)
17	IC-305970	3.69	6.81	2.28(3)	1.92(3)	1.03(1)	1.23(3)	1.03(1)
18	IC-383296	3.76	6.85	2.33(3)	1.93(3)	1.02(1)	1.23(3)	1.03(1)
19	IC-510984	3.75	7.01	2.34(3)	1.95(3)	1.0(1)	1.26(3)	1.05(1)
20	IC-52554	3.88	7.11	2.39(3)	2.01(3)	1.00(1)	1.23(3)	1.04(1)

Fig. 1 Scatter Diagram of Metroglyph Analysis in Sesame germplasm lines